

13TH ICAZ

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ABSTRACTS

2ND - 7TH SEPTEMBER 2018

ANKARA - TURKEY

13TH ICAZ INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

2ND – 7TH SEPTEMBER 2018

ANKARA – TURKEY

ABSTRACTS

A series of suggestions and drawings for the conference logo were submitted by METU, Ankara University and Hacettepe University students. After a vote by the members of the Scientific and Organizing Committee, the drawing proposed by Zeynep Ece Sahin was chosen. It encircles a number of bone "shadows" topped with the statue of a deer drawn after a metal find from the "Kings' tombs" at Alacahöyük. This statue is displayed at the Anatolian Civilizations Museum in Ankara.

International Council for Archaeozoology

Middle East Technical University

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

Late Neanderthal subsistence in Dalmatia: New data from Mujina Cave (Croatia)

Mujina Cave is a small cave located on a mountain slope above Kaštela, west of Split on the eastern Adriatic's Dalmatian coast. The site yielded rich vertebrate remains associated with a Late Mousterian lithic assemblage dated to c. 40-45 kyr (MIS 3; Rink et al. 2002). This study focuses on the larger vertebrate remains from the middle and lower stratigraphic contexts (E complex – Layers E1, E2A, E2B, E3A, E3B, and E3C) and compares them to the upper part of the sequence (Layers B, C, D1, and D2) analyzed in detail by Miracle (2005; Karavanic et al. 2008). Red and fallow deer are dominant throughout the E complex, although there are significant changes in their relative frequency that most likely correspond to changing palaeoecological conditions. The steppe rhinoceros (*Stephanorhinus hemitoechus*) is a significant addition to the species list. Detailed taphonomic analysis shows numerous traces of butchery, but also the evidence of the presence of non-hominin carnivores (e.g. cave bear, hyena, and wolf). The Mujina Cave faunal assemblage provides significant data for understanding Late Neanderthal hunting, food processing and consumption practices, and their sensitivity to changing palaeological and cultural conditions.

Keywords: *Middle Palaeolithic, Neanderthal, Croatia, hunting, cave, zooarchaeology*

Siniša Radović, Institute for Quaternary Palaeontology and Geology, Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Zagreb, Croatia. sradovic@hazu.hr

Preston Miracle, Department of Archaeology and Anthropology, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK. ptm21@cam.ac.uk

An inquiry into the “missing” Central Balkans Mesolithic: Faunal remains from Bukovac cave, Serbia

Apart from the well-known Mesolithic sites in the Danube Gorges, occupied more or less continuously between c. 9500-5500 cal BC, the evidence of human presence in the North-Central Balkans in the Early Holocene is virtually non-existent. This puzzling phenomenon has been associated with presumed low population densities, changing environmental conditions, geomorphological effects on site survival and visibility, or the lack of research. In that respect, recent excavations at the cave site of Bukovac near Despotovac in the Resava river valley (tributary of Velika Morava, Central Serbia) (Dogandzic et al. 2014; 2017) provide important new data relevant to the understanding of the phenomenon. The stratigraphic sequence at Bukovac is predominantly related to the Upper Palaeolithic (mainly Gravettian) occupancy, manifested by a rich lithic assemblage, hearths, bone tools and abundant faunal material. However, the Early Holocene use of the cave had also been confirmed, on the basis of partially preserved layer along the cave wall, containing animal bones which produced a Mesolithic date. Apart from dating, the taxonomic composition of the sample (including remains of wild game, mustelids, rodents, birds and a significant amount of fish bones) is unequivocally reflecting Early Holocene biodiversity and foraging (hunting and fishing) patterns. In this paper, we present the results of archaeozoological analysis of the faunal sample from the Bukovac Mesolithic layer, but also discuss the implications of its state of preservation in the broader context of Mesolithic „invisibility“ in the archaeological record.

Keywords: *Bukovac cave, Mesolithic, faunal remains, Central Balkans*

Ivana Živaljević, BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Serbia. ivana.zivaljevic@biosense.rs

Vesna Dimitrijevic, Laboratory for Bioarchaeology, Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, Serbia; BioSense Institute, University of Novi Sad, Serbia. vdimitri@f.bg.ac.rs

Tamara Dogandzic, Department of Human Evolution, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig, Germany; Department of Anthropology, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, USA. tamara_dogandzic@eva.mpg.de

Sahra Talamo, Department of Human Evolution, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig, Germany. sahra.talamo@eva.mpg.de

Dušan Mihailović, Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, Serbia. dmihailo@f.bg.ac.rs

Zooarchaeological evidence for the earliest records of Holocene cetaceans in the northern Black Sea

Archaeology provides the best baseline data for presence of the Black Sea marine fauna in the early to mid-Holocene, since the sea level was low, and now the sedimentation beds are covered by sea. Modern cetacean fauna of the Black Sea is comprised of the harbour porpoise *Phocoena phocoena*, the common dolphin *Delphinus delphis* and the bottlenose dolphin *Tursiops truncatus*. The time of their dispersal in the Black Sea is conventionally referred to the inflow of Mediterranean waters 9-7 kya (Moura et al., 2013; Fontaine et al., 2014). The earliest Holocene cetacean remains from the Marmara Sea, western and northern Black Sea are dated as 8 kya (Çakırlar, 2013; Haimovici and Balăşescu, 2006; Matskevoy, 1977): however, these fragmentary specimens are hardly identifiable by species. The earliest identifiable record of *Delphinus delphis*, represented by a mandible and vertebrae, comes from Durankulak (Bulgaria) (6.5-6.2 kya) (Manhart, 1998). Here we report the earliest identifiable record of *Phocoena phocoena* in the northern Black Sea from the Copper Age site of Laspi 1 in the southern Crimea (Ukraine), 5.6 kya, represented by morphologically diagnosable skull fragments and numerous vertebrae, which identification was confirmed by ZooMS collagen analysis, from a few animals. A few bones were used as decorations. These findings were a part of diverse assemblage of marine fauna which was different from freshwater fauna of preceding Mesolithic assemblage from the nearby located Laspi 7. This is the evidence of growing availability of marine resources and, possibly, dispersal of marine vertebrates in the Black Sea during the mid-Holocene.

Keywords: *Cetaceans, Black Sea, Holocene, Chalcolithic, marine resources*

Pavel Gol'din, Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. pavelgoldin412@gmail.com

Sergey Telizhenko, Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. telizharh@hotmail.com

Animal bones in the soot: The Zooarchaeology of Neolithic western Macedonia

For nearly eighty years, the region of western Macedonia, Greece, has been the centre of lignite mining. During the last twenty years, the Public Power Corporation (DEI) has funded a number of large-scale rescue excavations before proceeding to the destruction of archaeological sites for mining purposes. These excavations provided a unique opportunity to a new generation of Greek archaeologists to work during a period of immense financial crisis. From a purely scientific point of view, however, they produced important information for the prehistory of the region: apart from the quality of the material culture evidence recovered, the excavations yielded vast amounts of animal bones, the quantity of which has not been recovered from any other excavation in northern Greece. In terms of the available faunal data, therefore, the region of western Macedonia is ideal for exploring the nature of human-animal relationships during prehistory.

This study will present information on subsistence strategies from the region of western Macedonia during the Neolithic. It will take into consideration the faunal data from a number of sites dating from the early 6th to the late 4th millennium BC, discussing trends in animal management and placing Neolithic western Macedonia in its temporal and regional context. Within this region, the evidence suggests great variation in the use of animal resources, and vast inter-site differences regarding the scale and nature of livestock management. Overall, it is anticipated that this study will highlight the potential of zooarchaeology in the investigation of human Neolithic communities in a region that has for many years remained attached to the study of its classical past.

Keywords: *Neolithic, western Macedonia, Greece*